

The 3,4-dimethoxybenzalanilines were subjected to *in vitro*, activity test against various fungi. The Schiff bases having electron-donating substituents in the N-phenyl ring have shown remarkable activity against the fungi *Alternaria solani* and *Colletotrichum capsici*. Similar test of secondary amines have indicated that though they are active against the above mentioned fungi, they are less effective than the Schiff bases.

Experimental

Synthesis of 3,4-dimethoxybenzalaniline : A mixture of veratraldehyde (0.1 mole), aniline (0.1 mole) and toluene (125 ml) was refluxed till water (0.1 mole) had separated out. Distillation of the solvent gave a crude Schiff base which was recrystallised from methanol as white shining crystals, m.p. 83° (yield 100%).

Reduction of 3,4-dimethoxybenzalaniline : To a stirred solution of 3,4-dimethoxybenzalaniline (0.1 mole) in methanol (50 ml) was added an alkaline solution of sodium borohydride (2.0 g in 2 ml of 2 N NaOH diluted to 20 ml with distilled water) dropwise at a rate so as to keep the temperature between 50-60°. The contents were then cooled and kept overnight at room temperature. The excess of solvent was distilled off, the contents were cooled, diluted with water (100 ml), chilled in ice bath for 2 hr and filtered. The crude product was then recrystallised from methanol to give light yellow shining needles, m.p. 92° (yield 80%).

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Synthesis of 9-Alkyl-6-Mercaptopurine Analogues

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6-MERCAPTOPYRINE (6MP)¹, an antimetabolite with relatively low toxicity is widely used clinically to treat leukemia. The activity of 6MP substituted at the 9-position with normal alkyl and cycloalkyl groups were studied² earlier against a line of H. Ep2 cells and two sublines resistant to 6MP. It was found that the butyl, pentyl, cyclopentyl, hexyl, cyclohexyl, heptyl and octyl derivatives exerted inhibitory effect on all the 3 lines.

Friend Leukemia virus infection in mice was inhibited by 9-cyclopentyl-6-mercaptopurine³. It was of interest to study the effect of long chain alkyl substitution at 9-position of 6MP on tumour as it was observed that lipophilicity sometimes increased the activity of an anticancer drug when it could be modified by appropriate substitution⁴. This communication describes the synthesis of 9-undecyl (I), dodecyl (II), tetradecyl (III), hexadecyl (IV) and

Fig. 1. I. R=C₁₁H₂₃; II. R=C₁₂H₂₅; III. R=C₁₄H₂₉; IV. R=C₁₆H₃₃; V. R=C₁₈H₃₇

octadecyl 6-mercaptopurine (V) and studies on their effect *in vitro* against KB cells and *in vivo* against lymphoid leukemia L1210 and Sarcoma-180.

The above 6MP analogues were prepared by reacting thiourea in *n*-propanol with the corresponding 6-chloro-9-alkyl purines whose synthesis has been reported earlier⁵.

Experimental

The melting points were determined in open capillary tubes using a Thomas-Hoover Unimelt apparatus and are uncorrected. The ultraviolet spectra in ethanol and the infra red spectra in KBr were recorded in Pye Unicam SP8 100 and Perkin Elmer 177 spectrophotometer respectively. The experimental procedure being similar, the preparation of 9-undecyl 6-mercaptopurine is described here as a representative case.

6-Mercapto-9-undecyl purine (I) : A solution of 322 mg (1.04 mmole) of 6-chloro-9-undecyl purine⁵ and 100 mg (1.32 mmole) of thiourea in 10 ml *n*-propanol was heated under reflux for 1 hr and then cooled in ice bath. The precipitated solid was collected by filtration, washed with cold *n*-propanol and dried; yield 230 mg (72.0%), m.p. 260-64°. Two crystallisations of the crude material from ethanol gave the analytical sample (I), m.p. 265-66°. λ_{max} in nm 324. ν in cm⁻¹ (KBr): 2800-2000 (acidic hydrogen); 1600 and 1540 (C=C and C=N).

The physical characteristics of the different compounds prepared are given in Table 1.

Biological assay : All these mercapto compounds were tested against Sarcoma-180 in strain A mice. *In vitro* testings in KB cells and *in vivo* in lymphoid leukemia L1210 were carried out at National Cancer Institute, USA. None of the compounds, however, showed antitumour activity.

In vitro tests in KB cells showed ED₅₀ to be 1.0 × 10³ µg/ml for all the compounds, the criteria of activity being ED₅₀ ≤ 6 µg/ml. *In vivo* tests against Lymphoid Leukemia L1210 were carried out in BDF₁ mice at 5 different dose levels viz., 400,

TABLE-1

Compound	m.p. °C	Yield %	Formula	Analytical (%)						UV Absorption spectra λ_{max} in nm
				Calcd.			Found			
				C	H	N	C	H	N	
I, R=C ₁₁ H ₁₁	265-66	72	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ S	62.74	8.50	18.80	62.40	8.44	17.99	924
II, R=C ₁₁ H ₁₁	264-65	69	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ S	63.75	8.75	17.50	63.90	8.58	17.19	924
III, R=C ₁₁ H ₁₁	266-67	75	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ S	65.50	9.19	16.09	65.22	9.27	15.85	929
IV, R=C ₁₁ H ₁₁	263-65	76	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ S	67.03	9.60	14.90	66.75	9.65	14.73	925
V, R=C ₁₁ H ₁₁	261-64	74	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ S	68.31	9.90	13.86	68.40	9.69	13.58	923

200, 100, 50 and 12.5 mg/kg body weight and maximum survivality was shown by V at 400 mg dose level, the T/C was 114% whereas T/C $\leq$ 125% was considered active⁶.

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Chemical Investigation of the Stem Bark of *Canthium dicoccum*

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THE isolation of α -amyrin and oleanolic acid¹ and a new triterpene acid called canthic acid² from the stem bark of *C. dicoccum* Gaertn. Merr. (Syn. *C. didymum* Gaertn.) was reported earlier. The present communication reports the isolation of two coumarins, aesculetin dimethyl ether and scopoletin, and a triterpene acid sapogenin, acetyl ursolic acid from the same source.

The ethanolic extract of air-dried powdered defatted stem bark of *C. dicoccum* was concentrated and excess of diethyl ether was added to precipitate the crude glycosides. The ether layer was decanted off. Two compounds, compound-A and compound-B, were isolated from the ether soluble part by preparative tlc over silica gel G. The crude glycoside obtained from the ether insoluble part was hydrolysed with acid and the aglycone part was separated into acid and neutral parts. The acid part on column chromatography over silica gel gave compound-C.

Compound-A, C₁₁H₁₀O₄ (M⁺206), m.p. 145° [λ_{max} (EtOH): 229, 251, 257, 293 and 344 nm (log ϵ 4.27, 3.77, 3.68, 3.75 and 4.03 respectively). ν_{max} (Nujol mull): 1720 cm⁻¹ (coumarin lactone ring). ¹H NMR spectrum: (90 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 6.23 (1H, d, J=9.5 Hz, H-3), 7.58 (1H, d, J=9.5 Hz, H-4), 3.90 (6H, s, 2 x-OCH₃), 6.83 (1H, s) and 6.80 (1H, s) for H-5 and H-8. Mass spectrum: m/e 206, 191, 178, 163, 135 and 120] appeared to be 6,7-dimethoxy coumarin (aesculetin dimethyl ether)³ which was finally characterised by direct comparison with an authentic sample (m.p., mixed m.p., tlc and ir spectra).

Compound-B, C₁₀H₈O₄ (M⁺192), m.p. 204° [λ_{max} (EtOH): 230, 254, 260, 298 and 346 nm. (log ϵ 4.10, 3.65, 3.60, 3.65 and 4.07 respectively). ν_{max} (Nujol mull): 1706 cm⁻¹ (coumarin lactone ring) and 3360 cm⁻¹ (phenolic-OH). ¹H NMR spectrum: (80 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 6.25 (1H, d, J=9.5 Hz, H-3), 7.57 (1H, d, J=9.5 Hz, H-4), 6.20 (1H, s, phenolic -OH, partially merged with the doublet centred at δ 6.25, disappeared on D₂O exchange), 3.95 (3H, s -OCH₃), 6.89 (1H, s) and 6.82 (1H, s) for H-5 and H-8. Mass spectrum: m/e 192, 177, 164, 149 and 121] appeared to be 6-methoxy, 7-hydroxy coumarin (scopoletin)⁴ which was finally characterised by direct comparison with an authentic sample (m.p., mixed m.p., tlc and ir spectra).

Compound-C, C₂₃H₃₀O₄, m.p. 286-87°, formed a monomethyl ester, C₂₃H₃₂O₄ (M⁺312), m.p. 243-44°. It gave pink $\rightarrow$ violet colouration in Liebermann-Buchard test and a pale yellow colouration in tetranitromethane test. ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra of compound-C and mass spectrum of its monomethyl ester indicated the compound-C to be acetyl ursolic acid⁵ which was finally characterised by direct comparison with an